

Project Summary

Overview

This proposal seeks funding to convene, engage, and co-develop a critically-needed, low-tech, and sustainable framework for community specific data sharing practices with three geoscience disciplines: hydrology, oceans, and seismology. We will create a centralized web platform for discovering and accessing existing but disparate resources that will provide the activation energy necessary to infuse FAIR and Open Data and Science practices into current research workflows. The process will be researcher-driven, vetted and endorsed. The goal is to empower the target disciplines to be knowledgeable of, connected to, and adopt use of, their community's existing CI resources, technologies and leading practices; proactive in effectively and efficiently managing and sharing FAIR research outputs. The impact of this proposal will result in higher quality, interoperable data being shared through community-preferred disciplinary repositories, accessible for immediate reuse in data-driven research, including AI/ML applications. A Framework Toolkit, will serve as a template for additional disciplines demonstrating community readiness.

Project Outcomes (items 1-3 for each discipline) Include:

1. A Discipline-Specific Data and Digital Object Management Framework containing a vetted set of leading practices that are reviewed, approved, and mapped to the framework.
2. A neutrally-branded web platform of trusted content with the context to apply the information.
3. Engaged Discipline Leadership, Liaisons, and researchers that support and sustain the framework.
4. Framework Toolkit, with implementation guidance, for use by additional disciplines

Broader Impacts

This project will bring together key international discipline leadership, repositories, journal editors, and researchers focused on creating awareness and building capacity in FAIR and Open research practices within the geosciences. The result of which will facilitate a paradigm shift in the research lifecycle by actively integrating data sharing and repository collaboration early and throughout the lifecycle. It will form novel and sustainable partnerships between researchers, research cyberinfrastructure, and journal editors to improve the effectiveness and value of Open Science practices by bringing clarity to currently disparate data publication policies and requirements. Project outcomes will lower barriers, improve research data management and sharing practices, and foster a future data-savvy research workforce in alignment with NSF and other governmental Open Science strategies. The project will support an early career geoscience data professional by providing valued opportunities in Open Science leadership. Resulting products will be made open and shared broadly to allow other disciplines to replicate this approach, further amplifying the impact of this work.

Intellectual Merit

This proposed work investigates the current state of data resource coverage and workflows for data and software sharing stakeholders on a discipline-by-discipline basis to gain insights into current misalignments and inefficiencies. Knowledge gained will be leveraged to create discipline-specific resources that will improve efficiencies in existing research cyberinfrastructure and direct researchers to deposit data types and software in the proper repositories, the accessibility of which can extend solutions to the global research community. This work will advance FAIR data management and Open Science, integrating these practices into existing research lifecycles moving toward a stronger Geo- Open Science Ecosystem, evolving scientific habits and norms. The impact of this will improve the quality and reusability of publicly-accessible data, enabling robust research and education that would otherwise not occur; including the use of emerging data-driven AI and ML techniques that require high-quality interoperable data to solve complex Earth system challenges. These outcomes ultimately expand the benefit of NSF research investments.